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BREGILAB final report

Tasks of Work Packages 1, 3 and 6 carried out by VITO/SEB

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Table of Abbreviations

CAGR	Compound annual growth rate
CF	Capacity factor
CHP	Combined heat and power plant
COP	Co-efficient of performance
DSM	Demand side management
EH	Electric heater
EV	Electric vehicle
HP	Heat pump
LCOE	Levelized cost of electricity
O&M	Operation and maintenance
ORC	Organic Rankine cycle systems
PtG	Power to gas
PV	Photovoltaic
RE	Renewable energy
TS	Time-slice
VRES	Variable renewable energy source
WP	Work package

Introduction

Balancing the Belgian electricity system for maximal use of **Renewable Energy** generation by a **Grid Injection Limit Algorithm** and optimal **Battery** deployment (BREGILAB) started in 2018 as an Energy Transition Found project (ETF). The project was planned to be carried out by a consortium integrated by EnergyVille (IMEC, VITO NV, KU Leuven, U Hasselt and KMI). The experience and expertise of each partner and the further collaboration allowed the consortium to satisfactorily conclude the project and generate useful results, insights and recommendations.

The work allocated to VITO NV is divided into three different units based on the topic of expertise. SEB (Smart Energy & Built environment), SCT(Separation and Conversion Technology) and RMA (Spatial environmental aspects). This report is generated by VITO/SEB and provides results, analysis and additional information for the tasks and work packages led by it. In the centre of the research executed by VITO/SEB within BREGILAB, the TIMES-BE model takes a primary role. The report is organized starting from the description of the changes that TIMES-BE underwent to make it possible to answer the research questions from the results of a long-term, integrated and detailed energy system model. In the subsequent sections, we analyse the impact of hourly demand profiles, deployment of electricity-based technologies (electric vehicles and heat pumps), interconnection capacity, solar PV and wind penetration, and the use of renewable electricity to produce molecules. The description of how the sections in this report address the work packages and tasks of BREGILAB is described here below.

WP1: Scenario studies of RE Penetration using different algorithms

- T1.1 Model development for assessing the balance of the Belgian grid with high penetration of variable renewable generation (Section 1).
- T1.7 Impact of future e-mobility and residential heat pump deployment (Section 3)
- T1.8 Impact of interconnection capacity (import/export) on grid stability (Section 4)
- T1.9 Estimation of additional renewable energy capacity for 'power to gas' generation (Section 10)

WP3: Renewable energy generation

- T3.2 Wind onshore and offshore deployment evolution and availability factor (Section 5)
- T3.3 PV deployment evolution and availability factor (Section 5)
- T3.4 Correlation of wind and PV availability factors (Section 6)
- T3.5 PV availability factor optimization as a function of location (Section 7)
- T3.6 PV availability factor optimization as a function of orientation (Section 8)

WP6: Demand side data and future demands (VITO)

- T6.1 Extrapolation from historical data to future demand scenarios (Section 2)
- T6.2 Potential of industrial thermal demand for non-used RE (Section 9)
- T6.3 Potential of residential boiler heating for non-used RE (Section 3)
- T6.4 Scenarios for future e-mobility demand (Section 3)
- T6.5 Scenarios for future commercial and residential heat pump demand (Section 3)
- T6.6 Scenario for 'power to gas' generation for seasonal storage (Section 10).

1. Model development for electricity sector balancing on the Belgian grid

Assessing the adequacy of the power grid in the long-term in a situation with high share of variable renewable energy resources (VRES) is fundamental to evaluate the robustness and flexibility of the power sector. Nonetheless, the power sector will have to be able to respond to changes in the demand, not only its consumption patterns but the high electrification of the demand. This includes, but is not limited to, electric vehicles (EVs), heat-pumps (HP), electrolyzers, and electric furnaces. This is the reason for using an integrated model that covers the entire energy system and catches their interactions. These interactions are what is known as sector coupling –in the case of materials or energy exchanges– or indirect effects of sector-specific decisions. VITO/SEB has developed the TIMES-BE model, build on the experience and expertise of several researchers during several years. The model included all energy sector and their interactions, nonetheless, to properly answer the research questions explored in BREGILAB, it was needed to adjust the model. Almost all sectors went through a development process that led to more detail representations of energy end-uses, production processes, consumption profiles, sector interactions, and so on, as it is explained in this report in *section 2 - Extrapolation from historical data to future demand profiles*.

TIMES, as defined on its website¹, is a modelling framework used to model energy systems varying the spatial and temporal resolution (e.g.: regions, countries, hours, seasons, years) and allowing to develop both top-down and bottom-up models. On its website, the framework is defined as “*The Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System (TIMES)... developed as part of the IEA-ETSAP’s methodology for energy scenarios to conduct in-depth energy and environmental analyses (Loulou et al., 2004). The TIMES model generator combines two different, and complementary approaches to modelling energy: a technical engineering approach and an economic approach. In a nutshell, TIMES is used for, the exploration of possible energy futures based on contrasted scenarios*” (Loulou et al., 2005).” (ETSAP, 2005).

TIMES can represent the full value chain from import or mining of energy and material resources up to meeting final demands, either energy or products (e.g.: ammonia, glass, space heating, lighting). The modelling framework uses what is called commodities to represent the flow of energy carriers and materials between processes. These processes can represent transformation processes such as energy transformation processes such as electricity production, coke ovens, transmission and distribution equipment, biofuels production; or final energy consuming processes such as vehicles, industrial processes, light bulbs, refrigerators, boilers, air-cooling, etc. The processes, commodities and commodities flows are used to build the mathematical representation of the energy system, which is needed to optimize the Linear Program (LP). The LP includes the constraints defined by physics such as the balance between electricity demand and electricity generation in each period, as well as user-defined constraints such as maximum capacity, annual growth and emissions targets.

TIMES-BE works with a 5-year resolution to cover the period from the base year (2014) up to 2050. Within each year, it is needed to reduce the time resolution from 8760 hours to a lower number due to the computational burden of such models. In TIMES-BE, 120 periods are defined, these are called time-slices (TS). The TS structure is defined based on the relevant profiles such as national electricity demand, PV and wind profiles, and daily temperature. Thus, the TS structure is made by selecting the 10 most representative days with a 2-hour resolution. This is done by an optimization tool developed in the ETSAP community². Finally, the results of the model, and the defined scenarios, provide detailed information such as installed capacity, energy and material flows, marginal production cost, CO₂ emissions, investments and O&M cost needed to meet the demands in a cost-optimal manner (see Figure 1).

¹ <https://iea-etsap.org/index.php/etsap-tools/model-generators/times>

² https://iea-etsap.org/workshop/Sophia_Antipolis_Oct2015/10-ETSAP%20Representative%20days%20proposal.pdf

Figure 1. Schematic of TIMES inputs and outputs; source: (Remme et al., 2001). (ETSAP, 2005)

The TIMES-BE model has been developed by VITO for several years, incorporating insights and good practices from the projects in which the model has been used. To represent the impact of higher penetration of VRES in the energy system the model was modified to move from a national representation of wind and solar potential and availability to a provincial resolution, as can be seen in Figure 2. To do so, TIMES-BE now includes the capacity factor (CF) for wind (onshore and offshore) and solar PV, as well as the maximum installed capacity for each province. The CF dataset and the maximum theoretical capacity per technology are the output of WP3. The electricity transmission and distribution grid are represented as 'high voltage', 'medium voltage' and 'low voltage' with intermediate convertors and related conversion losses. The injection of PV generated electricity occurs at the level of connection: residential PV at low voltage; commercial and industrial PV at low and medium. Additionally, there is a differentiation between residential PV and commercial/industry PV, due to the tilt of such systems and their orientation (*see section 8 - PV availability factor optimization as a function of orientation*). The generated electricity is injected into the national grid, therefore, in this regard, there is no provincial differentiation as TIMES-BE assumes the grid to be a copper plate. However, with this configuration it is possible to identify the electricity injected into the grid from distributed PV as well as the flow between electricity voltage levels.

Figure 2. Power grid representation with provincial wind and solar PV in TIMES-BE.

2. Extrapolation from historical data to future demand profiles

2.1. Methodology

Energy services such as lighting, heating, cooling and cooking are the drivers that explain the evolution in electricity demand, both in terms of global consumption and temporal fluctuations. Energy service demands are represented with a high temporal resolution to reflect fluctuations in electricity demand. A calibration procedure is therefore used for matching with historical observed fluctuations in demand. Due to the scarcity of real-world data for producing an intra-year energy service demand profile, the calibration procedure is complex and requires data from different sources. For this reason, a stepwise explanation may be helpful for the reader:

1. It is important to collect two types of data: the hourly demand of the commodities (i.e., power or gas) which is powering the energy service demands of interest, and the yearly total demand for each energy service demand. The first type of data is obtained through the Synergrid³ dataset, which provides the profiles, with hourly definitions, of both power and gas consumption for the residential and commercial sectors. The second type of data, instead, comes from the JRC-IDEES database⁴, in the form of yearly energy consumption, per fuel and per end-demand.
2. The two types of data described above represent, respectively, the summation per end-demand and overtime of the researched profiles; as better shown in Figure 3. This type of problem is named *constrained matrix problem*.

Input data 2: Yearly total energy service demand for the commodity (sum over time)

Time	1	2	3	4	5	6 ...	N	Total
End demand profile 1 (for the commodity x)	[Hatched Area]							0.532
End demand profile 2 (for the commodity x)	[Hatched Area]							0.131
End demand profile 3 (for the commodity x)	[Hatched Area]							0.145
End demand profile 4 (for the commodity x)	[Hatched Area]							0.639
Total demand for the commodity x	0.124	0.241	0.068	0.122	0.174	0.079 ...	0.185	1.447

Input data 1: Time-series for commodity demand (sum over energy service demands)

Output: Energy service demands time series

Figure 3. Illustrative representation of a constrained matrix problem, with its inputs (sum of hourly profiles and yearly consumption)

3. In order to decompose the time series for the commodity demand and obtain the single end-demands time series, a methodology named biproportional input-output (or RAS) has been used. It is one of the most known methodologies for data reconciliation and has been used for similar purposes since the 1970s⁵. However, the methodology needs as an input –besides the total of each row and column– of a non-negative matrix (see Figure 3) and a synthetic profile per each end-demand so as to obtain a more realistic approximation of the end demands
4. The synthetic load profiles are therefore obtained with a specific tool, which requires as an input only an hourly time series of a typical day, and coefficients which determine the variability of that profile over the week (e.g.: the difference between weekdays and weekends) and over the seasons. The tool, then, generates four typical weeks through the provided coefficients, and linearly interpolates the weeks between them, giving as an output an hourly profile for the full year. The input data to the synthetic load profile generator comes from:

³ http://www.synergrid.be/index.cfm?PageID=16896&language_code=FRA

⁴ http://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ftp/jrc-opendata/JRC-IDEES/JRC-IDEES-2015_v1/

⁵ BACHARACH, Michael: (1970) Biproportional Matrices and Input-Output Change. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge

- a. An Intertek Report⁶ for the UK government, which already provides all the end demand profiles for space heating, water heating, cold appliances, lighting, cooking, laundry, dishwashing, and other appliances (which are the end demands of the residential sectors)

Figure 4: Operational flow chart for computing the demand profiles in the residential sector

- b. For the commercial sector, as similar sources were not available, a 2 steps process was adopted: first, a breakdown with the RAS methodology on the gas consumption per service in the sector, with initial conditions estimated based on expert knowledge; and a second RAS breakdown of the electricity demand per service, using the previously calculated gas demands as initial conditions for electricity use in thermal appliances (i.e. cooking stoves, space & water heating, based on the assumption that energy service profiles are the same regardless the consumed commodity). The non-thermal related electricity consumptions are also given initial conditions based on an educated guess.

Figure 5: Operational flow chart for computing the demand profiles in the commercial sector

⁶https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/208097/10043_R66141HouseholdElectricitySurveyFinalReportissue4.pdf

- Finally, all the hourly profiles are time-sliced, i.e., translated from the real world to the model time domain. This is realized with a Time-Slice Tool, which selects 10 representative days in a year and their weight, by minimizing the difference between the resulting TS profile and the original hourly time series. The choice is done accordingly to a finite number of time series, among which also the commercial and residential end demands are also present.

2.2. Electrical demand profiles

As a result of the methodology described above, the obtained end demand profiles are shown. In particular, it is relevant to focus on the electricity demand, as it covers (in some cases, as space heating and cooking, partially) all the end demands.

Figure 6: Electrical demand per end-use in the households sector during four typical days

The results in the figure above show the residential electricity demand per end-use. In order to show the variability of the results on a weekly and seasonal basis, four typical days are reported, two winter and two summer days, out of which one weekday and one weekend day.

The same graph is then proposed for the commercial sector end demands, always taking into account the four days of interest.

Figure 7: Electrical demand per end-use, in the commercial sector, in four typical days

It is important to remark that the data shown above are introduced to the model as calibration for the base year (2014). For the following years, the model is able to invest in several technologies per each sub-sector. Therefore, the graphs will sensibly vary both in the total electrical demand, as well as in the single contributions (end demands).

3. Modelling and impacts of mobility electrification and building heating

Electrification of transport and building heating are two of the key factors for the decarbonization of, respectively, the transport and building sectors. They can be realized, in the future, only with increasing penetration of electric vehicles (EVs) for transport, and heat pumps (HPs) for building heating. In the two following sub-sections, they will be presented (with the main assumptions and modelling choices in TIMES-BE) and studied in their individual impact (EVs in section 3.1 and heating electrification in section 3.2). Finally, the combined impact of EVs and HPs is investigated in section 3.3.

3.1. Electric vehicles (EVs)

3.1.1. Modelling approach and main assumptions

In the transport sector, and in particular, in road transport, electric options are made available for all the end demands. More specifically, for passenger cars, both battery electric vehicles and plugin hybrid vehicles are available, while for buses (both urban and intercity) and trucks, only the battery vehicle option is available, as well as for the motorbikes. These technologies are included in TIMES-BE as shown in Figure 8. Buses, trucks and motorbikes electric solutions are modelled on an annual level, without specifying intra-year demand fractions (which are therefore supposed to be constant over time)⁷. This is mainly done due to the lack of data in terms of intra-yearly use of these devices (some of them, such as electric trucks, are not fully commercialized), and as it anyways represents a reasonable assumption: if, in fact, a large portion of trucks travels equally during day and nighttime, for buses and motorbikes, given their low number, the impact on the energy system of their time-specific use is considered as negligible. The modelling approach for the competing technologies is the same.

Figure 8: Transport sector available technologies, per final demand (EVs highlighted)

The battery-based passenger cars, available from 2020, are modelled with a higher level of detail with respect to the other EVs. In fact, they are split into four sub-categories, depending on the driving habits (Commuting/Non-Commuting) and the amount of km driven (Long/Short Distance). In addition to this, the modelling structure has one more level of complexity: Charger technologies use electricity from the building sectors (through a Home Charger and a Work Charger) to charge the battery of each car typology (with the distinction between Commuting Cars, which can be charged both at home and at work, and non-Commuting cars that only chargeable at home). For the moment, no public chargers are considered as no profiles of this type of chargers were available. The chargers in TIMES-BE are represented as Smart, which is the most cost-efficient charging strategy, planned by a central decision-maker (the model solver). This means that the model chooses when to charge the car batteries, with the only limitation of the availability of the cars either at work or at home.

⁷ The yearly demands have been computed starting from data on stock of cars/bus/trucks/moto (from TMLLeuven), on their use (Federal Planning Bureau) and on their efficiency (JRC-IDEES) and checking the consistency with Eurostat Energy Balance data

An additional run has been realized with partially non-smart chargers: they reproduce the necessity, for some users, to charge their cars at specific times, regardless of the electricity price, while for the rest of the time they behave as smart chargers. Finally, batteries' output is available to the end demand technology (BEV themselves), which is characterized by a demand-specific availability factor⁸. The full scheme is reported in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Electric passenger cars modelling structure

To exemplify the linkage between the availability of the charging (both at home and work) and the Availability Factors (AFs) of the cars, Figure 10 is reported, showing the AFs for the chargers and cars of one specific demand.

Figure 10: Long-Distance Commuting Cars (and Chargers) Availability Factors

The modelling approach for the competing technologies (including the plugin hybrid vehicles) is similar, as they are also characterized by AFs, but they are not linked to any charger or battery technology.

⁸ The availability factors have been built starting from the yearly demand and a time series for passenger car use coming from the studies in the framework of the ROLECS project (a similar approach has been used for the availability factors of the chargers)

3.1.2. Model results

A huge penetration of electric mobility (E-mobility) is no longer questioned, having a major impact in terms of global demand and on-demand fluctuations, but the pace of implementation remains highly uncertain. According to the results of TIMES-BE, in terms of the number of vehicles, the penetration of EVs may see a relevant jump between 2025 and 2040, when motorbikes (2030), passenger cars (2030-2035) and trucks (2035-2040) undergo the steepest increase in the transition.

Figure 11: Uptake of electric vehicles, per vehicle type

By 2030 E-mobility might therefore increase Belgian electricity consumption by 9%. However, relatively little research has been done on the impact of E-mobility on electricity demand fluctuations, taking into account that the average occupancy of a car is less than 10%, creating opportunities for stabilizing the network. With this purpose, two scenarios have been designed for the sake of comparison: 1) only smart chargers, and 2) with partially non-smart chargers (whose use is forced at some times to pre-defined AFs to reproduce the necessity of some users to charge their cars regardless of the electricity price, i.e., evenings for residential chargers, morning and noon for commercial chargers). The result is, as Figure 12 shows, a very fluctuating chargers load profile for the Smart charging scenario, as the model prefers to heavily invest in EV chargers to be able to use them fully only when the power price is low. On the other hand, the Forced charging scenario shows a more stable charging load profile. This is due to the fixed AFs in some hours, which prevent the model from using the chargers only when the electricity price is low, reducing the amount of investment capital, and consequently forcing the model to charge some cars also when power prices are higher.

Figure 12: Power consumed by EV chargers in the two scenarios

This phenomenon has direct consequences in the home and commercial sectors, where electric passenger vehicles are charged. In these sectors, as explained more extensively in section 3.3, chargers can be fed by the power grid, or from local electricity production, through PV + battery systems. The level of installed capacity for both PV and batteries (home + commercial) is comparable among the scenarios, as noticeable in Figure 13 (even though batteries see a +20% investment in 2050 in the Forced charging scenario).

Figure 13: Installed capacity of PV and batteries in Belgium (home + commercial)

However, the use of the storage changes with the scenario to match the changed EVs charging profile. While in the reference scenario there is a more punctual match between PV production peaks and EVs charging peaks, with a limited charging of batteries, which is shifted to lower production moments. In the Forced charging scenario, batteries charge during peak PV hours and are discharged to cover EV charging during non-peak hours. Therefore, the impact of E-mobility demand can be mitigated by local power production and storage, with users' charging habits softly influencing the local investments, as well as the way of using the storage devices.

Figure 14. Hourly profile of PV production and EVs charging. Results from TIMES-BE.

3.2. Heat pumps (HPs)

3.2.1. Modelling approach and main assumptions

Heat pumps (HPs) are modelled in several sectors: the main one is the building sector, where they represent an important option for space heating, space cooling and water heating; however, they are also included in the agriculture sector, for both low-temperature heat purposes, and greenhouse heating. Finally, in the industry, heat pumps can substitute fossil fuels-based boilers in many low-temperature applications, in the following subsectors: chemicals, food, construction, machinery, mining, textile, wood, paper and others.

Several heat-pump technologies have been included in the model, here divided per end demand:

1. Residential - Heating: Ground heat pump (both with and without cooling option), Air heat pump (both with and without cooling option)
2. Residential - Cooling: Non-reversible HP + (see above)
3. Residential - Water heating: Air heat pump
1. Commercial – Heating: Air heat pump with electric boiler (both with and without cooling option), Advanced air heat pump with electric boiler (both with and without cooling option), Ground heat pump with electric boiler (both with and without cooling option)
2. Commercial – Cooling: Non-reversible HP + (see above)
3. Commercial – Water heating: Air heat pump
1. Agriculture – Low enthalpy heat and greenhouse heating: Ground heat pump
1. Industry – Several subsectors: Air heat pump

Figure 15: Residential sector available technologies, per final demand (HPs highlighted)

Figure 16: Commercial sector available technologies, per final demand (HPs highlighted)

Figure 17: Agriculture sector available technologies, per final demand (HPs highlighted)

Most of the heat pump technologies are modelled as a demand process, with, as an input, ambient heat (or ground heat in the case of ground heat pumps). However, there are some modelling differences between the heat pumps in the building sector and the ones in agriculture and industry.

For the latter ones, indeed, some simplified assumptions have been used:

- For the industrial HPs, as the temperature difference between the ambient and the output of the HP itself is significantly more constant than in a building, the efficiency is set as a constant value; furthermore, being the industry sector built on annual values (instead of time-slicing the demands and processes availability), the heat pumps are not characterized by any availability factor
- These assumptions are valid, for similar reasons, also for the agriculture sector HPs

On the other hand, for the heat pumps in the building sector, a time-slice-level availability factor is defined to reproduce the level of use of the heat pumps, which is set to the same level as the other heating devices⁹.

Moreover, the efficiency of the ambient air heat pumps for space heating has been characterized by a time-slice level of detail, accordingly to the weather data. In the graph below, the efficiency (COP) of these heat pumps is reported, per type of building. It is possible to notice how, during the winter, the efficiency of the HPs can lower up to 40%, while during summer it is stably at the nominal value.

Figure 18: Efficiency of building heat pumps over the year

This does not apply to ground heat pumps, which have a fixed efficiency, under the assumption that the ground temperature is constant throughout the year.

3.2.2. Model results

Analysing the results of the TIMES-BE model with Net-Zero 2050 assumptions, it is possible to notice how, although heat pumps are present and have an impact also in the agriculture and industry sectors, their main presence and contribution, as one would expect, will take place in the building sector.

Concretely, looking at the installed capacity, building heat pumps may remain the vast majority of the HPs total capacity installed, moving from slightly more than 5 GW in 2020 to almost 35 GW in 2050, when the sum of all the other contributions (agriculture + industry) remains below 3 GW in 2050.

⁹ For the residential sector, the availability factors for space heating technologies come from the postprocessing of the Intertek 2012 residential survey and the Synergrid power and gas profiles in residential appliances. For the commercial sector, a similar procedure has been used, starting from Synergrid non-residential profiles on power and gas consumption (see T6.1)

Figure 19: Heat-pumps installed capacity per subsector

Moreover, within the building sector, the main contribution in terms of installed capacity is represented by the space heating heat pumps, whose uptake is always increasing starting from 2030 (residential sector) and 2040 (commercial sector). On the other hand, water heating HPs represent a cost-effective solution only when the emission constraint becomes more stringent (2050).

The most interesting impact of heat-pumps installations on the energy system happens in their interaction with the power market. Heat pumps cover, especially during winter months, a large portion of the power demand, strongly influencing its price. This is particularly visible in the graph below, where 2030 and 2050 intra-year power demand from heat pumps has been compared with electricity prices.

Figure 20: Intra-year power consumption from HPs - coupled with power price

In this framework of highly volatile electricity demand (especially in the day-night and seasonal alternation) and consequent prices, it may be of interest to use heat storage technologies to reduce the negative impact on the power prices and the demand peaks.

In order to do so, an exogenous approach has been used with respect to the TIMES model: in fact, being TIMES an optimization model reproducing perfect foresight in investment and operation, its solver would operate (in charging and discharging the buffer) in the most convenient hours, but this is unfortunately not possible for a real-world user.

Therefore, to be more adherent to the real case, by using the TIMES output concerning the intra-yearly data on power price and consumption shown in the previous graph, a simple scenario with heat buffers has been built. It has been based on the following assumptions:

- Only a portion of the installed heat pumps has a heat buffer; this percentage is left as an optimization variable;
- In a given time slice, all heat pumps which are not in use to produce demand heat and that have a heat buffer connected, can be used to charge the buffers; moreover, all heat pumps working at a low regime can switch to a higher working regime (with a maximum, common to both buffer-ed and buffer-less HPs, of 80% of rated power) to use the heat surplus to feed the heat buffer;
- Heat buffer capacity is set to be equal to the inflow capacity (which is supposedly equal to the HP rated-power) with charging and discharging time equal to 1.40 hours¹⁰ (this value comes from the technical data of the Joule Cyclone 500, which has also been taken as a reference for the economic data for the residential sector)
- Heat losses are considered on an hourly basis (and with a unit value according to the Cyclone 500 value)
- For the commercial sector, a bigger buffer tank has been considered (Joule Buffer Tank 5000) with the hypothesis of proportionality of input flow/storage and unit losses.
- Each heat buffer system is provided with a smart meter, which decides when to charge and discharge the heat buffer:
 - Charging takes place when the electricity price is lower than the seasonal average (with a percentual difference which has also been left as an optimization variable)
 - Discharging takes place whenever it is needed, with a constraint on the maximum discharging heat power = maximum charging heat power.
- The following economic data are taken:
 - Investment cost: 56€/kW
 - O&M costs: disregarded (can be included in heat pump O&M costs)

The cost-optimal solution, as it is possible to see in the table below, shows a medium level of penetration of buffers among the total number of heat pumps for both residential and commercial sectors (even if in absolute terms, the installed capacity of heat buffers will be higher in the residential sector due to the higher number of heat pumps). However, the data which differs the most is relative to the price decrease to enable the smart meter. In fact, for the commercial sector, a higher sensitivity of the smart meter leads to higher economic convenience of the device.

	Residential Heat Pumps	Commercial Heat Pumps
<i>Heat pumps – Total installed capacity [GW]</i>	35.6	13.2
<i>Portion of HPs with buffer [%]</i>	31.3	46.2
<i>Price decreases necessary to enable the smart meter [%]</i>	16.1	1.5
<i>Net Present Value [M€]</i>	99.20	28.22
<i>Total monetary savings on fuels consumption, compared with buffer-less scenario [%]</i>	6.87	5.00

Nevertheless, for both residential and commercial sectors, installing a number of heat buffers represents a cost-optimal solution. In the graph below it is possible to see how the intra-yearly graph for power consumption changes in this scenario, again in 2030 and 2050. In fact, in this case, the highest consumption peaks can be noticed immediately after each time electricity prices decline, while short periods with high electricity prices see a very important reduction in power consumption, as in the central time-slices of 2050.

¹⁰ <https://www.jouleuk.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/CYCLONE-INSTALL-MANUAL-01.pdf>

Figure 21: Intra-year power consumption from HPs - coupled with power price (cost-optimal scenario with heat buffers)

3.3. Impact of HPs and EVs on Belgium's energy system

While the importance of heat pumps and electric vehicles remains undiscussed, their impact on the energy system, and more specifically on the power sector, could be extremely relevant, especially if considering very aggressive future decarbonization scenarios. In particular, in the case of a net-zero scenario by 2050, the electricity demand from HPs and EVs explodes, going from the current levels (3.7 TWh, 4% of the final energy consumption) to over 60 TWh in 2050. The contribution of heat pumps and electric vehicles in 2050 is almost identical, but the latter has a faster uptake: in 2030, chargers for passenger cars may consume around 5.3 TWh (considering both home and commercial installations), while the uptake of new industrial heat pumps to produce process heat (especially in the food sector) brings a power consumption of 2.5 TWh. Later, with the electrification of heavy-duty vehicles, the power consumption of road transport sets to very high levels: 25.3 TWh in 2040, and 29.5 in 2050.

Figure 22: Power consumption from EVs and HPs, per sector/technology

Consequently, the increase in power consumption may have an impact on the stress level of the power grid. In order to limit it, and to avoid very high investments in new infrastructure, the model can choose to install and run sector-specific PV plants (and battery storage technologies), whose produced power can be used “behind the meter”.

Figure 23: Power consumption (positive) and generation (negative values) at a local level. In red, the contribution which comes from (or goes to) the grid in 2030 (a) and 2050 (b)

Figure 23 provides the relevant information to better analyse the impact on the grid. It shows the consumed power in each sector’s technologies (heat pumps and electric vehicles), as well as the locally produced power. It is possible to see how the increase in power consumption in 2030 and 2050 is coupled with an increase in installed PV capacity (14 GW in 2030, 96 in 2050), able to provide production peaks of more than 10 GW in 2030 and over 35 GW in 2050.

This makes the four end-sectors produce more electricity than consuming from the grid for HPs and EVs, but with quite many unbalances between summer days, when the grid is provided with almost 8 GW (20 GW in 2050), and cold winter nights (see S01), when the demand from the grid overcomes 5 GW (12 GW in 2050). Therefore, the overall impact on the power grid of the uptake of electricity-based technologies in road transport and heating will be mitigated by the contribution of local PV plants; however, in some extreme conditions, the demand of these devices may not be compensated by the intermittent production input, requiring an extra effort to the power grid.

4. Impact of interconnection capacity (import/export) on grid stability

To cope with the variability of solar and wind, the use of a robust interconnected grid is paramount. The European Commission identifies the relevance of the interconnection between member states to increase the share of variable renewable energy sources (VRES) and thus reduce curtailments. The European Commission has set a target of 15% of interconnection capacity¹¹ for each member state by 2030 (European Commission, 2018). In TIMES-BE, the import and export capacities were defined according to the Ten Years Network Development Plan (TYNDP) published by ENTSO-E in 2022 (ENTSO-E, 2022). The interconnection capacity indicator for Belgium can be seen in Table 1, as it can be noticed, the interconnection target is reached by 2030 and continues at a value above the requested threshold. The interconnection indicator does not include the solar distributed PV capacity, which towards 2050 becomes highly relevant in TIMES-BE power generation capacity.

	units	2020 ¹²	2030	2040	2050
Main activity	GW	18.40	16.95	22.96	38.87
Auto producers	GW	7.30	4.55	4.62	4.89
total installed capacity	GW	25.70	21.50	27.58	43.76
Interconnection capacity	GW	3.6	8.9	13.0	13.0
Interconnection to local power capacity ratio¹³	[%]	13.8%	41.3%	47.2%	29.8%

Table 1. Power installed capacity and interconnection capacity TIMES-BE results.

Since TIMES-BE geographical representation is limited to Belgium, it was necessary to use a dispatch model developed by the *Katholieke Universiteit Leuven* (KUL) to cover the integrated European electricity market. The results of this model were integrated into TIMES-BE to represent the availability and price for imported electricity, as well as the price and willingness to consume exported electricity in other member states. Additionally, the import capacity is limited to the values defined by the TYNDP data. To analyse the importance of the future interconnection capacity in the energy system, especially to provide flexibility, Figure 24 shows the utilization profile of the import capacity. As can be noticed, the use of the import capacity increases over time. On an annual basis, the capacity factor (CF¹⁴) increases from 0.08 in 2030 to 0.25 by 2050 (see Table 2). Besides the utilization factor, it is important to understand in which periods the transmission import capacity is used, and how it complements the local generation. In Figure 25 it can be seen that the interconnection capacity is used throughout the year and it doesn't follow a clear pattern. While comparing the use of interconnection capacity with the availability of VRES it is possible to identify that during the winter electricity imports compensate for the low availability of solar PV. On the other hand, as during the summer wind availability is much lower and PV is only used during day hours, it is necessary to import electricity, especially during evening/night hours.

Parameter	unit	2020	2030	2040	2050
<i>installed capacity</i>	GW	3.50	8.88	13.03	13.03
<i>Imported electricity</i>	TWh	3.98	6.48	24.85	28.93
<i>Utilization Factor</i>	-	0.13	0.08	0.22	0.25

Table 2. Import capacity utilization factor in TIMES-BE.

¹¹ The 15% cross-border capacity ratio corresponds to the import capacity over EU countries' installed generation capacity.

¹² Installed capacity from EUROSTAT. Interconnection capacity from ELIA website. Future values taken from TIMES-BE results .

¹³ The import to local power generation capacity factor is calculated as the ratio between the total maximum import capacity in GW and the summation of the total capacity of Main activity producer electricity only and CHPs, Autoproducer electricity and CHPs. In other words, the import capacity must be equivalent to given percentage of the total electricity production capacity without considering distributed PV.

¹⁴ The capacity factor (CF) is calculated as the ratio of the actual electricity flow through the transmission line and the maximum annual flow. The maximum annual flow is given by the installed capacity and the maximum operating hours, accounting for mandatory or essential maintenance to the transmission line, also known as availability factor (AF) ($\text{Max.Flow}[\text{GWh}] = \text{Capacity}[\text{GW}] * \text{AF}[-] * 8760[\text{h}]$)

Import capacity utilization factor

Figure 24. Import capacity utilization factor.

Note: 2020 values are taken from the ELIA website(ELIA, 2020). 2030, 2040 and 2050 are TIMES-BE results.

Electricity imports

Figure 25. Import of electricity throughout the year.

Note: 2020 values are taken from the ELIA website (ELIA, 2020). 2030, 2040 and 2050 are TIMES-BE results.

When it comes to the use of the export capacity (which, according to TYNDP projections, will be lower than the import capacity), its behaviour is the opposite of the import capacity. In this case, the utilization factor initially falls to zero in 2040 (see Table 3). However, towards 2050, electricity exports increase again, mainly due to the high electrification of the demand and high VRES installed capacity. Although this is clean and unexpensive electricity, the system is not able to accommodate more electricity as the pumped storage, batteries and EVs are at maximum capacity during those periods. Furthermore, electricity exports occur during 4449 hours in 2030 and 1965 hours in 2050, although with different uses of the maximum capacity as can be seen in Figure 26.

Parameter	unit	Today	2030	2040	2050
Installed capacity	GW	2.30	7.88	11.53	11.53
Exported electricity	TWh	14.60	0.88	0.00	8.23
Utilization Factor	-	0.72	0.01	0.00	0.08

* Data from Eurostat 2019

Table 3. Export transmission capacity and utilization.

Export capacity utilization factor

Figure 26. Export capacity utilization factor.

Results from TIMES-BE show the relevance that developing the interconnection capacity will have for the energy system, especially to cope with extreme weather events by importing electricity from neighbouring countries or by exporting excess electricity rather than curtailing it. Nevertheless, the utilization factors of such assets remain low in the long-term, reaching 0.25 in 2050 in the case of import capacity. This is because batteries and hydrogen turbines provide flexibility to the system. Thus, electricity imports are concentrated during the evening and night, especially during winter and spring.

Electricity exports

Figure 27. Import of electricity throughout the year.

Note: 2020 values are taken from the ELIA website. 2030, 2040 and 2050 are TIMES-BE results.

The increase in the Belgian electricity demand together with the future power generation mix makes that in some periods, especially during the winter, the power market relies on imports from neighbouring countries. Nonetheless, the transmission lines are never used at their maximum capacity. What is important to highlight, though, is the increase in the long-term capacity factor (or utilization rate) of the infrastructure, as shown in Figure 26. This is mainly driven by the increase of VRES' share in the total electricity generation mix. Additionally, in some cases electricity imports might be more attractive than local production, in particular on windy days across the whole of Europe, to meet electricity demand or to charge batteries, EVs or produce molecules. Moreover, it is important to align the reinforcement of the Belgian transmission grid with future interconnection needs to avoid grid congestions, which are not captured by TIMES-BE. Finally, total exports decrease with the decommissioning of the remaining 2GW of nuclear power plants by 2035. This increase again toward 2050 to allocate solar PV generation during summer days.

5. Solar PV, wind onshore and offshore deployment evolution and availability

The work package 3 of BREGILAB explores the future renewable energy generation, in particular the impact that the availability of wind and solar will have on their deployment. The data generated in WP3-T3.3 (See Bregilab renewable potential tool¹⁵) is used in TIMES-BE to study the role that renewables will have in the future energy system. Since there is an annual variation of wind and solar availability, and TIMES-BE works with only one availability profile for all the periods in the modelling timeline (2014-2050), it is necessary to evaluate the possible impact that such variations can have on the dispatch and generation mix of the power sector. 2012 was selected as the weather year to be used in TIMES-BE as it was considered to be the most representative year within the period 2006-2019. Thus, this report explores the possible impact that higher, or lower, availability of renewables can have on the electricity generation mix starting from TIMES-BE results for 2030.

As can be seen in section 6 - *Correlation of wind and PV availability factors*, the availability of wind and solar PV changes from year to year. In this case, it is important to understand how the actual capacity factor might impact the variable renewable energy source (VRES) generation and the merit order in the power dispatch. Table 4, Table 5, Table 6 and Table 7 show the annual variation of renewable generation by province, considering the availability profiles and results from TIMES-BE and the minimum and maximum capacity factor between 2006 and 2019, according to the data gather in the BREGILAB-Work package 3. When the capacity factor (CF) from TIMES-BE results is lower than the minimum CF, it can be interpreted as renewable curtailments. The maximum technical capacity is also relevant to assess the use of the resources and validate at which moment TIMES-BE makes use of the VRES resources. As expected, in the long term, the wind is a very attractive resource for the model as can be seen in Figure 28. By 2040 and 2045, wind offshore reaches its maximum capacity, while the onshore is mostly constrained by the annual growth threshold set in TIMES-BE. Conversely, solar PV leaps to more than 90 GW in 2050, from around 45 GW in 2045. This is the result of the electrification needed to reach deep decarbonization in this last period. Nonetheless, from the system perspective, both technologies complement each other during the day and throughout the year to meet the electricity demand profiles.

Figure 28. Solar PV and wind growth from 2020. From TIMES-BE results.

In the case of solar PV, the provinces with a higher CF variation are West-Vlaanderen, Luxemburg and Limburg. In 2030 the difference between the actual CF in TIMES-BE and the minimum and maximum possible CF from the weather years data (2006-2019) ranges between -12% to +23%, while in 2050 it is between -3% and +42%. The lower actual CF in 2050 is the result of solar PV curtailments across several provinces. Nevertheless, while putting the variation in perspective, and absolute values, Liege and Limburg are the regions with more output variation in 2030, 1.03 TWh and 1.12 TWh respectively. In 2050, Antwerpen and Oost-Vlaanderen have a variation of 3.3 TWh each. These variations might indicate which provinces can experience an increase in renewable electricity generation from one year to the other, which should

¹⁵BREGILAB: Renewable Energy in Belgium, VITO, 2022. <https://www.energyville.be/en/bregilab-renewable-energy-belgium> .

be considered while reinforcing the power transmission and distribution grid, as well as the location of batteries within the system. Furthermore, in a year with good weather conditions, the difference in output might be enough to cover 3% (2.7 TWh) of the electricity demand in 2030 and 11% (19.9TWh) in 2050. In the case of wind, there are no curtailments neither in 2030 nor in 2050, since this energy resource is used at its maximum capacity in TIMES-BE due to the fact that wind generation profiles don't have high generation peaks as PV. Therefore, electricity generation from windmills matches more the total electricity demand profile. Nevertheless, in a year with high wind availability, such as 2007 or 2015, it could be possible to cover 2.5% more of the electricity demand in 2030 and 2050, 2.3 TWh and 4.7 TWh respectively, compared with TIMES-BE results.

Province in 2030	Generation [TWh]	Installed capacity [GW]	Actual CF in TIMES-BE	min average CF	max average CF	Output variation (min-results) [TWh]	Output variation (max -results) [TWh]
Antwerpen	0.80	0.81	0.1129	0.1121	0.1300	-0.006	0.121
Brabant Wallon	0.14	0.13	0.1198	0.1154	0.1332	-0.005	0.016
Brussels	0.12	0.12	0.1148	0.1128	0.1319	-0.002	0.018
Hainaut	0.35	0.35	0.1141	0.1145	0.1310	0.000	0.052
Liege	9.37	9.05	0.1181	0.1103	0.1311	-0.618	1.028
Limburg	6.37	6.41	0.1135	0.1122	0.1334	-0.071	1.117
Luxembourg	0.16	0.16	0.1164	0.1023	0.1308	-0.020	0.020
Namur	0.23	0.22	0.1198	0.1125	0.1310	-0.014	0.021
Oost-Vlaanderen	0.82	0.83	0.1133	0.1143	0.1308	0.000	0.128
Vlaams-Brabant	0.46	0.44	0.1186	0.1148	0.1327	-0.014	0.055
West-Vlaanderen Continental	0.65	0.67	0.1105	0.1222	0.1362	0.000	0.150
West-Vlaanderen Kust	0.12	0.12	0.1140	0.1246	0.1400	0.000	0.027
TOTAL Belgium	19.59	19.59	0.1142	0.1103	0.1302	-0.751	2.753

Table 4. Solar PV generation, capacity, actual capacity factor and output variation per province in 2030. From TIMES-BE results.

Province in 2050	Generation [TWh]	Installed capacity [GW]	Actual CF in TIMES-BE	min CF	max CF	Output variation (Min-results) [TWh]	Output variation (Max -results) [TWh]
Antwerpen	16.34	17.18	0.1086	0.1121	0.1300	0.000	3.223
Brabant Wallon	3.03	3.06	0.1131	0.1154	0.1332	0.000	0.538
Brussels	4.20	4.27	0.1122	0.1128	0.1319	0.000	0.736
Hainaut	8.25	8.99	0.1047	0.1145	0.1310	0.000	2.070
Liege	9.00	9.05	0.1135	0.1103	0.1311	-0.254	1.392
Limburg	9.35	9.66	0.1105	0.1122	0.1334	0.000	1.935
Luxembourg	2.81	3.09	0.1039	0.1023	0.1308	-0.043	0.728
Namur	4.12	4.42	0.1062	0.1125	0.1310	0.000	0.958
Oost-Vlaanderen	14.28	15.40	0.1058	0.1143	0.1308	0.000	3.381
Vlaams-Brabant	8.94	9.44	0.1082	0.1148	0.1327	0.000	2.033
West-Vlaanderen Continental	5.74	6.82	0.0961	0.1222	0.1362	0.000	2.400
West-Vlaanderen Kust	1.29	1.49	0.0984	0.1246	0.1400	0.000	0.544
	87.34	87.34	0.1073	0.1136	0.1318	-0.297	19.939

Table 5. Solar PV generation, capacity, actual capacity factor and output variation per province in 2050. From TIMES-BE results.

Province in 2030	Generation [TWh]	Installed capacity [GW]	Actual CF in TIMES-BE	min average CF	max average CF	Output variation (min-results) [TWh]	Output variation (max - results)[TWh]
Antwerpen	0.65	0.36	0.2035	0.2061	0.2626	0.000	0.188
Brabant Wallon	0.93	0.41	0.2592	0.2269	0.2774	-0.116	0.065
Hainaut	0.82	0.43	0.2180	0.2111	0.2563	-0.026	0.144
Liege	0.42	0.22	0.2203	0.1683	0.2103	-0.099	-0.019
Limburg	0.39	0.28	0.1621	0.1988	0.2518	0.000	0.217
Luxembourg	0.13	0.09	0.1661	0.1442	0.1850	-0.017	0.015
Namur	0.54	0.29	0.2118	0.1766	0.2121	-0.090	0.001
Oost-Vlaanderen	2.76	1.30	0.2412	0.2187	0.2757	-0.257	0.394
Vlaams-Brabant	0.13	0.07	0.2166	0.2141	0.2695	-0.002	0.031
West-Vlaanderen Continental	2.99	1.35	0.2540	0.2279	0.2853	-0.307	0.370
West-Vlaanderen Kust	0.50	0.19	0.3017	0.2446	0.3023	-0.095	0.001
Offshore	16.38	4.60	0.4066	0.3680	0.4281	-1.554	0.866
	26.64	9.58	0.3173	0.2880	0.3444	-2.562	2.272

Table 6. Wind generation, capacity, actual capacity factor and output variation per province in 2030. From TIMES-BE results.

Province in 2050	Generation [TWh]	Installed capacity [GW]	Actual CF in TIMES-BE	min average CF	max average CF	Output variation (Min-results) [TWh]	Output variation (Max -results) [TWh]
Antwerpen	4.21	2.18	0.2209	0.2061	0.2626	-0.282	0.795
Brabant Wallon	0.94	0.41	0.2624	0.2269	0.2774	-0.127	0.054
Hainaut	5.77	2.75	0.2392	0.2111	0.2563	-0.676	0.414
Liege	3.90	2.29	0.1945	0.1683	0.2103	-0.523	0.318
Limburg	3.63	1.80	0.2307	0.1988	0.2518	-0.501	0.333
Luxembourg	0.53	0.43	0.1421	0.1442	0.1850	0.000	0.160
Namur	4.04	2.34	0.1970	0.1766	0.2121	-0.419	0.310
Oost-Vlaanderen	6.85	3.07	0.2550	0.2187	0.2757	-0.974	0.559
Vlaams-Brabant	1.60	0.72	0.2540	0.2141	0.2695	-0.252	0.098
West-Vlaanderen Continental	2.84	1.21	0.2680	0.2279	0.2853	-0.426	0.184
West-Vlaanderen Kust	0.45	0.19	0.2686	0.2446	0.3023	-0.040	0.056
Offshore	28.61	8.00	0.4082	0.3680	0.4281	-2.818	1.390
	63.37	25.38	0.2850	0.2534	0.3060	-7.04	4.67

Table 7. Wind generation, capacity, actual capacity factor and output variation per province in 2050. From TIMES-BE results.

The impact of VRES availability can be observed in the dispatch of resources in the power sector. In this case, the marginal technology might be displaced in certain moments, which is captured in TIMES-BE in the merit order for different time-slices. Figure 29 shows how the availability increase for solar and wind might influence the dispatch, resulting in different electricity prices, emissions and primary energy use in the power sector. Solar availability was assumed to increase by 14%, (see Table 4), while the wind was assumed to vary by +8% (see Table 6). In these two cases, increasing the VRES capacity factor during the selected time-slices might lead to the use of less expensive generation technologies based on fossil fuels such as gas or liquid fuels. The impact of wind variation during the period S02Q06 (second representative day, between 10:00 and 11:59) is not representative since the wind participation in this period is less than 1%. On the contrary, solar covers 59.4% of the demand during these two hours, and it could have a higher impact on electricity prices. In the event

that both wind and solar availability reach a high CF, the capacity of other technologies displaced could be approximately 1.4 GW.

A different case can be observed in S10Q07 (tenth representative day, between 12:00 and 13:59). During these hours wind covers 52.0% of the demand while solar represents 21.2%. The generation capacity displaced by higher wind and solar availability is 0.83 GW. These differences are enough to lower the expected marginal price in the Day-Ahead market.

Figure 29. Wind and solar availability factor effect on merit order in selected time-slices in 2030 in TIMES-BE

6. Correlation of wind and PV availability factors

To complement the work done in Tasks 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 (PV and wind availability and maximum technical capacity), and to analyse possible impacts of low availability of variable renewable energy sources (VRES), a Dunkelflaute analysis was carried out. A Dunkelflaute (German word) is defined as an event where the availability of wind and solar is remarkably low for extended periods. However, there is no common, accepted definition of the three parameters that characterize a Dunkelflaute: i) wind availability, ii) solar availability, and iii) length of the period. As expected, with high penetration of VRES, a Dunkelflaute event becomes more likely to happen, therefore, the design of future energy systems should consider the reliability and adequacy of the system to cope with such events. This is why the concept of Dunkelflaute has been covered by TSOs in Australia (Energy Networks Australia, 2021), ENTSO-E and ENTOSO-G (Ziegenhagen, 2020), and ELIA (ELIA, 2017); as well as by the academia.

The starting point of the analysis was the data gathered in Tasks 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3, which consists of satellite information of 40 years from the Royal Meteorological Institute (KMI) database for wind and solar. The data were treated to compute the capacity factor (CF) of 14 years for PV and wind for 11 provinces in Belgium. At the national level, it is possible to see the spreading of the annual average CF for both wind and PV (see Figure 30), as well as the heterogeneity of the wind-PV combination. The dispersion of CFs for wind is higher than for solar. Some years stand out for solar PV generation, 2018 and 2019. While for wind generation, if comparing 2010 (lowest value) with 2007 or 2015, there is a difference of 10%. In other words, assuming the same installed wind capacity, it is possible to have an increase of up to 10% of total output. TIMES-BE works with the same CF profile for all years and this annual variation for future years is not included.

Figure 30. The annual average capacity factor for wind and solar PV.

To continue with the analysis¹⁶, and with the aim to reach a higher geographical representation of the variation across provinces, the wind and solar CF were calculated for each province. The CFs per province and year are depicted in Figure 31. Due to the difference in wind speed in West Flanders, the province was split into continental and coastline areas. The CF are similar across provinces as the land extension of Belgium is small when compared with other countries such as Germany, Sweden or Italy, where the regional differences are more notorious. Nonetheless, it is expected that in a national DF event there will be more renewable energy available in some parts of the country, which might be advantageous to minimize the impact of wind and solar low availability.

¹⁶ Due to the size of the raw data, a MATLAB script was used to compute average CF per province.

Figure 31. Wind and solar capacity factors per province and year in Belgium.

As mentioned before, the characterization of the Dunkelflaute has a strong impact on the number of events that can be identified in one year and the occurrence over time. Figure 32 shows the load profile for wind and solar PV, which are used to identify the number of hours in which the CF is below a pre-established threshold. In this case, while comparing the number of hours in which the CF is below 0.2 with the moments when CF is lower than 0.1 it is possible to see that not only there is a considerable change within the year (600-800 hours), but also significant variations across years (200-400 hours). As expected, the stricter the criteria on CF, the fewer Dunkelflaute events will be encountered. Several combinations of the three Dunkelflaute parameters were explored to define the criteria of the event (see Figure 33). From these combinations, the case in which the availability for both wind and solar was less or equal to 0.1 for a period of 24 hours was selected to be further explored with TIMES-BE.

Figure 32. Wind and solar load duration curve per year at the national level.

Figure 33. Dunkelflaute events over the year for several Dunkelflaute parameters definitions.

Additionally, to the Dunkelflaute definition, it was assumed that such an event must simultaneously happen in the 11 provinces. With these strict criteria, it was possible to identify that on the 8th of January a Dunkelflaute event, as previously defined, happened across all provinces as can be seen in Figure 34. In TIMES-BE, the 8th of January was included as part of the time representation structure in the model as one representative day¹⁷ and a special scenario with the time-slice structure including a Dunkelflaute was simulated.

Figure 35 shows the behaviour of the power sector, highlighting the Dunkelflaute day. In 2050, it is expected that the share of VRES will be higher, which might lead to an intensified impact of low wind and solar availability on the energy system. From Figure 35 can be noticed that gas power plants, CHPs and import capacity are used at their maximum capacity to compensate for the reduced output of wind turbines and solar PV. Additionally, the optimized use of EVs charging and pumped hydro storage provides another source of flexibility to the system while guaranteeing that electricity and transport demand is met. Hence the crucial role of smart charging, and the deployment of storage facilities.

Figure 34. Occurrence of Dunkelflaute ($CF_{wind} < 0.1$, $CF_{solar} < 0.1$, for 24h) in all Belgian provinces and at the national level.

¹⁷ TIMES works with a time-slice structure that is built by an optimization process that selects the most representative days to reduce the time resolution, and thus the computational burden, while staying close to the detail hourly profiles. TIMES-Be works 120 time-slices that are defined from the predefined 2 hours resolution and the 10 representative days selected by the optimization tool.

Figure 35. Power generation, pumping hydro storage and EV charging results from TIMES-BE in 2050.

The impact of a Dunkelflaute event on the energy system is not neglectable, which is why further analysis with different tools is important (e.g.: dispatch and adequacy models), as well as tracking down the progress made on this particular topic. From the results here shown, it is possible to conclude that flexibility sources will become more relevant, such as smart charging (with and without aggregators), use of batteries, interconnection capacity, and demand response (especially from the large industrial process). All these flexibility sources combined might help to cope with the scarcity of clean electricity. One limitation of TIMES-BE while analysing extreme weather years is the fact that the annual profile is static and therefore the event is happening on the same day each year. However, TIMES-BE provides enough insights about the design of the energy system as the model defines the needed power generation capacity that must be available to cope with a Dunkelflaute. A more detail study exploring the occurrence of extreme events with stochastic dispatch and adequacy models could complement the results of this study for the Belgian case. Furthermore, the analysis of a European Dunkelflaute is interesting for future studies, which might analyse how different regions are complementary to each other and whether the foreseen European interconnection capacity is enough to provide electricity to Belgium during such extreme events.

7. PV availability factor optimization as a function of location

Even though Belgium does not have a large geographical area, there are slightly weather differences among provinces, which translates into different availability factors of solar PV and wind (see section 6 - *Correlation of wind and PV availability factors*). Since TIMES-BE is an optimization model, it is expected that the cheapest or more beneficial technologies will be deployed first. In the case of solar PV, availability is the main differentiation parameter as economic parameters are common across provinces. An additional criterium taken into account in the optimization is the match between generation and demand profiles. In other words, TIMES-BE may select investments in a province with a better hourly profile rather than in another with a slightly higher capacity factor, which leads to an optimal result. Nonetheless, generations profiles and consumption patterns are very similar across all provinces, which reduces this effect. Thus, it is relevant to understand the impact of having a more even, similar growth across provinces and deviating from the optimal results from TIMES-BE. To this extend, and starting from TIMES-BE results, an all-provinces even growth is compared to the optimal solution found by the model. It is important to acknowledge the limitation of the power grid representation in TIMES-BE, which has a large impact on results. Hence, TIMES-BE results might be considered carefully and compared with the results of the power-grid model that include the detailed topology of the electricity network.

Figure 36 shows the evolution of installed capacity by region and the moment that maximum capacity is reached. Liege, Limburg and Namur are the provinces that reach their maximum capacity the soonest, Liege by 2025 and Limburg and Namur by 2030. On the other hand, West-Vlaanderen and Hainaut are used towards the end of the modelling period (2045 and 2050), without reaching their maximum potential as their average annual availability is lower than in other provinces. Nevertheless, these results should be interpreted carefully as the topology of the Belgian power grid is not highly detailed in TIMES-BE and electricity demand is not modelled at the province level. Further analysis might be needed to assess the stability of the power transmission grid and identify possible grid congestions. A more challenging analysis is required at the distribution level since most of the installed solar PV is distributed, which is partially covered in Work Package 2 of the BREGILAB project.

Figure 36. Solar PV installed capacity by province (left) and usage of maximum capacity (right) from TIMES-BE results.

As incentives are distributed across Belgian provinces, a more even deployment of the capacity across provinces might be likely. For this reason, the results from TIMES-BE were compared with an exogenous calculation of such distributed, even deployment. In this case and starting from the capacity installed in 2020 in TIMES-BE, the objective was to provide the same electricity output while having the same annual growth in all provinces. This results in a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) between 2020 and 2050 of 9.8%, however, it is much higher in 2030 and 2050 when electricity demand increases dramatically due to the electrification of the demand and industrial processes (See Table 8). Figure 37 shows the results of the assumed even growth for the provinces in Belgium. As it can be noted, the installed capacity in West-Vlaanderen, Hainaut and Oos-Vlaanderen starts to be relevant already from 2030, which is not the case in the TIMES-BE

results (see Figure 36). Moreover, the even deployment of the solar PV capacity leads to reaching the maximum capacity in most of the regions by 2050 and not sooner.

	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
CAGR	3.2%	24.0%	11.9%	4.9%	2.0%	14.2%

Table 8. The compound annual growth rate of installed PV capacity in Belgium from TIMES-BE.

Figure 37. Solar PV installed capacity by province (left) and deployment up to maximum technical potential (right) assuming evenly distributed deployment.

Finally, another important metric to compare the optimal deployment from TIMES-BE and the assumed even deployment is the cost of the generated electricity. For this purpose, the LCOE¹⁸ is a general acceptance and commonly used approach. As can be seen in Figure 38, the LCOE from TIMES-BE results is lower in all periods, which suggests that deviating from the optimal case might result in a higher system cost as more capacity is needed to guarantee the same electricity output in regions with low PV capacity factors. Approximately 0.7-1.1 GW of additional PV capacity will be needed, besides other additional investments to handle the excess in batteries to avoid VRES curtailments. This increase in installed capacity results in an LCOE difference of 0.8-3.9% between 2025 and 2045. By 2050, as installed capacity is alike, the LCOE difference shrinks and becomes almost negligible.

¹⁸ The Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) is a measure of the average net present cost of electricity of a generator over its technical lifetime, and it is calculated as the discounted summation of total costs over the lifetime divided by the total electricity generation over the same period.

Solar PV LCOE

Figure 38. Average solar PV LCOE for TIMES-BE results and the assumed even growth.

8. PV availability factor optimization as a function of orientation

Two important aspects are defining the characteristics of the installation of solar PV: the tilt angle -which defines the inclination of the panel concerning the horizon- and the orientation. The best tilt angle is different for each location and maximises the solar radiation on the panel. In the same way, the orientation influences the amount of radiation on the panel, which translates into higher output and hourly profile. Some studies found that installations with a higher orientation towards the south and a higher tilt angle might increase electricity output by 5.6%-17.3% (Khoo et al., 2014) (Babatunde et al., 2018). In TIMES-BE, solar PV installations were split into residential and commercial-industrial as it was assumed that the tilt angle is different in those sectors. The tilt in the residential sector is assumed to be 35°, while in the commercial sector it is 10°. Additionally, the profile used in TIMES-BE reflects the distribution of PV towards the south, east and west for both sectors. In the residential sector 71% of solar PV capacity points toward the south, 24% toward the west and 5% toward the east. In the commercial-industrial sector, the distribution is assumed to be even between east and west (50% each). As can be seen in Figure 39, the average hourly and average monthly availability vary considerably depending on tilt angle and orientation. The case with higher electricity output is when the panel is oriented toward south with a tilt angle of 35°, which is the case in the residential sector. The electricity output of this setting is 21.9% higher than the average off all configurations. However, this profile presents a pronounced peak in the middle of the day, 34% higher than the average, which is not fully aligned with the typical demand profile in the residential sector.

Figure 39. Capacity factor profile for PV by sector and orientation. Left: the average capacity factor by month. Right: the average capacity factor by the hour.

As mentioned before, the match between generation and demand is crucial to guarantee the stability of the distribution grid and maximise the use of green electricity. However, this is not possible without the use of flexible sources such as home and utility-size batteries, smart charging of EVs and novel electricity market designs¹⁹ (more information about flexibility sources can be seen in section 3). Comparing the electricity demand of the residential sector with the estimated electricity output of solar PV in 2030, it is possible to see that there is a mismatch between the peak in the residential sector, including EV charging, and the different orientations (see Figure 40). In the case of the TIMES-BE profile, there is an average excess of electricity of 11.1 GWh distributed in 8 hours. However, if all PV panels were oriented towards the south the excess of electricity flowing into the grid would be 13.6 GWh. In the other cases, the excess of electricity is much lower, being this 6.4 GWh, 6.7 GWh and 3.64 in the case of 100% east, 100% west and 50% east-50% west respectively. In these cases, electricity generation is on average 6 GWh lower than the TIMES-BE profile (31 GWh). The effect of the orientation can be also perceived throughout the year as it is shown in Figure 41. In this case only when PV panels are 100% oriented toward the south the total annual generation is higher than demand, while in all other cases there is a deficit of electricity, especially during winter months.

¹⁹ Other Energy Transition Found projects explore the design of future electricity markets such as EPOC. The project combines the expertise of 14 Belgian academic partners to improve the current state-of-the-art energy models, providing a consistent calculation for the long-term energy future in Belgium. <https://www.epocbelgium.be/en>

Figure 40. Hourly average residential demand and PV profiles by orientation in 2030 from TIMES-BE results.

Figure 41. Annual profile of average residential demand and PV profiles by orientation (using the 10 representative days in TIMES-BE) in 2030 from TIMES-BE results.

One of the most accepted metrics to compare electricity generation technologies is the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE)²⁰. In this case, this metric allows the comparison of the average electricity price generated from a solar PV installation based on orientation. Nevertheless, it is important to mention that another important aspect is the generation profile. In this regard, the orientation with higher output is towards the south, but the generation peak, as mentioned before, doesn't match any of the consumption peaks of the residential sector. Table 9 shows the average electricity generation by orientation for the commercial and residential sectors in TIMES-BE for 1 GW of installed capacity. It can be noticed that 100%S in the residential sector and 100%W in the commercial sector are the configurations with higher electricity output. Nevertheless, this doesn't always result in the best configuration for both sectors. Another useful metric is Self-Consumption (SC), defined as the fraction of the self-consumed PV electricity to the total PV electricity production (Fachrizal and Munkhammar, 2020). Thus, $SC = C / (B + C)$, where C is the consumed electricity from PV and A is the consumed grid electricity (see Figure 42). Therefore, by reducing the PV generation peak (B in Figure 42) and spreading the output along the day in more periods the SC increases, although with lower total electricity output.

²⁰ The Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) is a measure of the average net present cost of electricity of a generator over its technical lifetime, and it is calculated as the discounted summation of total costs over the lifetime divided by the total electricity generation over the same period.

Figure 42. Schematic outline of daily load (A + C), PV generation (B + C), and self-consumed electricity (C), (Fachrizal and Munkhammar, 2020).

On one hand, as can be seen in Figure 43 (a), the 100% south case has the lowest LCOE. However, this configuration also has the lowest SC . On the other hand, the LCOE of the 50%W/E configuration is around 30% higher than the 100%S. Noteless, the profile matches the residential demand profile as can be seen in Figure 40. While comparing these profiles with TIMES-BE, it can be seen that the assumed distribution (71%S, 24%E, and 5%W) decreases the LCOE while keeping a relatively high SC (see Table 10). The configuration with the highest SC is 50%W/E, which reaches a value of 0.75, that is 40% higher than the 100%S configuration and 28% higher than the TIMES-BE configuration. Nonetheless, when batteries are installed, EVs charging is possible and injection into the distribution grid is allowed, both 100%S and TIMES-BE configurations are the more appealing configurations from the energy system perspective as more and cheaper electricity is available. Still the possible impacts on the distribution and transmission grid must be carefully taken into account.

Figure 43. LCOE for residential and commercial/industrial solar PV installations by orientation from TIMES-BE.

	Unit	Residential	Commercial/ Industrial
<i>TIMES-BE</i>	TWh	1.242	1.035
<i>100% S</i>	TWh	1.312	-
<i>100% W</i>	TWh	0.893	0.995
<i>100% E</i>	TWh	1.105	1.075
<i>50% W/E</i>	TWh	0.999	1.035

Table 9. The average electricity output of 1 GW of solar PV for residential and commercial/industrial sectors by orientation.

	PV south	PV east	PV west	PV TIMES	RSD W-E
SC	0.536	0.707	0.581	0.586	0.757

Table 10. Self-Consumption factor for different residential PV orientations.

As the current PV capacity is predominantly south-oriented in TIMES-BE (71%), the case in with the panels are set pointing south has limited gains in electricity output (7%) and LCOE (1.9-3.5 €/MWh), still it creates more structural and physical problems for installations (these additional installation costs are not considered), which reduces the gains by electricity output. In the case of the 50% W/E configuration, there is a drop in electricity output (-20%)m which from the system perspective is a loss of opportunity. On the other hand, for the owner this configuration leads to lower dependency on electricity from the power grid, and, therefore, lower exposure to Day ahead market prices. House batteries integrated into PV will change these results as PV system owners will prefer higher output rather than a more distributed generation profile.

9. Potential of industrial thermal demand for non-used renewable electricity

The industry was responsible for 26% of the final energy demand in Europe (EU-27)²¹, being heat the dominant end-use. According to Fraunhofer, in 2012, process and space heat combined represented 71% of the total energy demand in the industry (TrustEE project, 2016). Therefore, the use of clean electricity at low prices is deemed to be appealing for the industrial sector to cover part of the thermal demand. In this case, when the electricity price is lower than traditionally used fuels (e.g.: natural gas), the partial or full production of heat by electricity might be economically beneficial for large industrial actors. Another advantage of the partial electrification of the industrial heat demand is the possibility to accommodate higher shares of variable renewable sources (VRES), as higher shares of VRES will request more flexibility from the electricity system. This flexibility might be regarded as the capability of the electricity system to adjust the generation or consumption of one particular process or unit in response to certain signals such as grid frequency, network congestions, or electricity prices. The latter denotes, every year with more impetus, the need to engage the demand as a source of flexibility, particularly in large industrial processes which might be able to modify their process output as a response to price signals. This is called demand side management (DSM). DSM can be classified as temporal flexibility (e.g.: production rescheduling) or spatial flexibility (e.g.: distributed consumers such as data centres) (Heffron et al., 2020). In this regard, part of the gas-based industrial process and space heat might switch partially or completely to electricity to benefit from electricity prices, reduce VRES curtailments and abate related GHG emissions.

The idea to use low-price electricity to produce heat has to be evaluated on the basis that the industrial processes are flexible or that heat can be stored to be used later on. The latter supposes some challenges such as developing materials that can achieve high-temperature density, durability, charging and discharging rates, and thermal storage (Ge et al., 2014) (Li et al., 2021). Nonetheless, thermal storage can provide the link between power and thermal grids through conversion systems such as heat pumps (HP), electric heaters (EH) or Organic Rankine Cycle systems (ORC) (De Schutter and Van Bael, 2019). Another aspect limiting the use of flexible heat supply from electricity is the production profile of the industry, which in the case of big production sites tends to be constant throughout the year. On the contrary, the energy consumption of smaller industrial process fluctuates more (e.g.: weekday and weekend, working hours and non-working hours, day and night). Hence, the question that arises is whether it might be possible for some industries to reschedule production as a response to process signals, especially in the cases where electricity is a dominant factor of production cost and there is spare production capacity.

In some industries the share of energy cost in total production cost can be on average close to 10%, as it is the case of pulp and paper, cement and lime, clay building materials and glass (European Commission. Directorate General for Energy. et al., 2020). For instance, in Chile, medium-size pulp and paper producers adjust their production according to electricity price signals (see Figure 44), concentrating production on weekdays (Valdes and Ramirez Camargo, 2021). According to the Fraunhofer institute, food, paper and other industries, which mainly consume low-temperature heat, accounted for approximately 30% of the total demand for heat and cooling in Belgium in 2012 (Fraunhofer ISI, 2017). However, as natural gas consumption in the industry -which might be mostly linked to thermal demand- is constant through the year (see Figure 45) and gas prices present high volatility throughout the year (see Figure 46), it might be assumed that industrial processes don't respond to natural gas price variations; in other words, their demand is inelastic. Nevertheless, the recent exponential increase of natural gas prices has led some specific industrial processes to reduce output or to momentarily halt production^{22 23}.

²¹ Calculated from Eurostat energy balance report.

²² Large Belgian steel producer stops production due to high energy prices, restart is unclear. https://www.nieuwsblad.be/cnt/dmf20220825_95288012

²³ BASF readies more ammonia production cuts in gas supply crunch. <https://www.reuters.com/business/energy/basf-considers-more-ammonia-production-cuts-gas-supply-crunch-sources-2022-07-27/>

Figure 44. Total electricity demand food industry (Valdes and Ramirez Camargo, 2021).

There are two approaches to provide flexibility to the system and benefit from low electricity prices and VRES high availability. On the one hand, the modification of the process output as it is the case in the food and paper industry in Chile. And on the other hand, by decoupling demand and supply by including a buffer to store thermal energy (the case for the building sector is explained in section 3 - *Modelling and impacts of mobility electrification and building heating*). Heat pumps can provide flexibility to the distribution feeder based on price signals by implementing a central coordinative control (Bhattarai et al., 2014) or by utilizing thermal storage (water tanks) and setting favourable operating boundaries (Fischer et al., 2017). Another alternative to reduce the dependence on fossil fuels for heat production is the installation of solar collectors for industries that require mostly low-temperature heat such as food, paper and textiles. In the case of the food industry, solar technology might not be able to support the total heat demand, nonetheless, it can pre-heat the water flowing into conventional heat sources, thus reducing the external energy demand of the system (Ismail et al., 2021). For the most part, storage tanks are needed to decouple demand and supply, benefiting from lower electricity prices. Despite economic savings on operating costs, complex storage systems should be designed depending on the specific temperature needs and consumption profiles of each production process, as well as being backed up for demand peaks by other devices such as electric heaters (Marcel Ulrich, 2021).

Figure 45. Domestic consumption in winter 2019/2020 (FLUXYS, 2021)

Figure 46. Dutch TTF Natural Gas price between March 2019 and February 2020.

Considering an industrial process with a thermal demand of 2 MW, it is possible to identify the impact of switching from a standard gas boiler to heat pumps (HP) or a combined system heat pump plus storage tank (HPST). As described before, it is assumed that the thermal demand of the process is flat during the day. Assuming the gas price for the industry in Belgium to be on average €16.59/MWh (PWC et al., 2020), and considering that gas nomination provides a daily price, there is no price fluctuation in the case of a gas boiler (GB: Gas Boiler low gas price). TIMES-BE includes the impact of the current geopolitical situation on natural gas price as can be seen in Table 11, which has an important effect on the final heat cost from this energy vector. To assess the impact of higher natural gas prices an additional case (GB_{hpg}: Gas Boiler high gas price) is included. Moreover, it is important to include the estimated price of CO₂ emissions, which increases the cost of natural gas-based technologies, which in TIMES-BE is estimated to be €150/tCO₂ in 2030. On the other hand, using network and additional costs at €38.8/MWh (PWC et al., 2020) on top of average electricity prices from TIMES-BE in the Day Ahead market, it is possible to estimate the average heat production cost in both cases HP and HPST. In the case of HPST, a tank that can provide 20% of the thermal demand is defined to be 500 kW_{th}, with a maximum storage capacity of 1h (500kW_{th}), and with an availability factor of 0.9. In this case, to guarantee that the heat pump can in certain periods of low electricity prices meet the thermal demand and inject energy to the storage tank to be used later on, it is necessary to increase also the capacity of the heat pump. As can be seen in Table 12, in a greenfield analysis, natural gas-based heat production remains the cheapest option. Nonetheless, heat pump technologies are closer in 2030 and could be expected to be cheaper by 2050. Finally, when adding a storage tank to take advantage of low electricity prices, seems to increase the average heat production cost, which can be explained by the increase in the investment costs –associated with the storage tank and the scaling of the heat pump– and the energy losses in the tank.

Commodity	Unit	2018	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Natural Gas ²⁴	€/MWh	27.16	33.86	72.15	38.52	35.26	34.99	34.99	34.99

Table 11. Natural gas price assumptions in TIMES-BE by 5 years milestone period.

	Capacity	Efficiency	CAPEX	OPEX	life	Heat output	Energy input	Energy Cost	CAPEX + FIXOM (annualized)	Heat cost
	[kW]		[€/kW]	[€/kW]	[yr]	[MWh]	[MWh]	[k€]	[k€]	[€/MWh]
GB ²⁵	2222	92%	193	3.9	25	17,520	19,097	895	38.9	53.33
GB _{hpg}	2222	92%	193	3.6	25	17,520	19,097	1,247	38.9	73.40
HP ¹³	2222	2.5 (COP)	435	8.7	25	17,520	7,008	943	87.9	58.88
HPST	HP	2722	2.5 (COP)	435	8.7	25	17,520	7,034	90.2	59.07
	ST ²⁶	500	85%	12	0.2	30				

Table 12. Comparison of heat production cost using gas boilers, heat pumps and heat pumps with storage tanks.

The results from TIMES-BE show that heat pumps are an interesting technology to meet the low-temperature and mid-temperature heat demand in the industry. Nonetheless, this technology follows the production profiles as the benefits from price differences are not attractive enough to modify production schedules. A limitation is the lack of data regarding

²⁴ Gas price assumption for 2022 is €125/MWh. TIMES-BE works with the average of 5 years to define the price for the milestone period.

²⁵ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/824592/industrial-fuel-switching.pdf

²⁶ https://ease-storage.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/EASE_TD_HotWater.pdf

spare capacities in sectors such as paper, textiles and food. Moreover, as the energy cost share is not a dominant part of the total production cost as can be labour cost or raw materials, it is expected that industry heat demand will remain inelastic. Nevertheless, it is important to mention that highly electrified processes such as steel, aluminium, chlorine, and future electrification such as electric naphtha crackers can benefit more from price and VRES fluctuations. In this regard, results from TIMES-BE exhibit that in moments where the electricity generation from VRES is high, the use of charging facilities for EVs, distributed batteries and H₂ production results in more attractive cases than heat production (see sections 3 - *Modelling and impacts of mobility electrification and building heating* and 10 - *Assessing the potential of PtG for seasonal storage and meeting future molecules demand*).

10. Assessing the potential of PtG for seasonal storage and meeting future molecules demand

Power-to-gas (PtG) has been seen as an alternative to reduce variable renewable energy source (VRES) curtailment and reduce the use of fossil fuels. It is important to notice that PtG uses in all cases (e.g.: gas hydrogen, ammonia, methanol) hydrogen as the main energy carrier, either pure or synthesised other molecules. Hydrogen can be included in the energy system either directly by blending hydrogen into the gas grid or by the so-called methanation process²⁷, which uses an external source of CO₂ and H₂ to produce methane (CH₄), which is similar to natural gas. As mentioned by Mazza, A. et al, the reinforcement and expansion of the existing power grid suppose some challenges and opposition, therefore, the use of the existing extensive natural gas grid could help to accommodate more VRES into the energy system (Mazza et al., 2018). Nevertheless, some barriers should be overcome to guarantee the deployment of PtG (or PtH₂), such as high investment cost, availability of cheap and clean electricity, storage and transport of H₂, and water availability, among others (Hu et al., 2020).

One of the above-mentioned barriers is the availability of clean and low-price electricity for PtG. In this regard, the assessment of curtailed electricity, electricity price and share of renewables can provide some insight into the potential of using PtG as a means to inject and store clean electricity. Although in TIMES-BE the PtG routes are available, both power-to-gas-to-power and power-to-H₂-to-power, none of these alternatives was selected in the period 2020-2050. As can be seen in Figure 47, the increase of VREs in the system modifies the price curve towards 2040 and 2050. However, the number of hours with low electricity prices remains low, which hinders the massive deployment of electrolyzers, as well as increases the curtailed electricity (see Table 13). The clean electricity in the model is either exported or used through EVs (see section 3 - *Modelling and impacts of mobility electrification and building heating*), batteries and pumped hydro storage. Moreover, once electrolyzers are part of the market it is expected that electricity prices will be different to the ones obtained in the central scenario.

Figure 47. Price duration curve TIMES-BE BREGILAB for 2030, 2040 and 2050.

²⁷ The methanation reaction was discovered by Sabatier and Senderens in 1902. In the presence of a nickel catalyst, hydrogen and carbon oxide react at elevated temperatures to produce methane and water. The reaction is strongly exothermic and rapidly approaches equilibrium, which is the most determining aspect regarding the layout of methanation processes. The main challenge for the methanation reactor is to handle the massive heat release from the reaction, putting high demands on either the temperature resistance of the catalyst or the heat transfer properties of the reactor or both. (Seemann and Thunman, 2019)

	Parameter	Unit	2030	2040	2050
Electricity Price	Max	€/MWh	284.33	472.21	275.61
	Average	€/MWh	88.74	84.92	84.90
	Min	€/MWh	39.17	0.00	5.77
	<40 €/MWh	Hours	691	1514	2363
	<20 €/MWh	Hours	0	513	575
	<15 €/MWh	Hours	0	513	289
	<10 €/MWh	Hours	0	513	289
Curtailments	Curtailed Electricity	GWh	0.0000001	0.0000003	41.94
	Hours with curtailments	Hours	-	-	216
	Electricity price during curtailments	€/MWh	-	-	5.8

Table 13. Summary of electricity price and energy curtailments in 2030, 2040 and 2050.

The production of H₂ is linked to access to inexpensive electricity and high utilization factors. The IEA estimates that an electrolyzer should operate more than 4000 hours a year, equivalent to a utilization factor of 0.46, to reduce the impact of investment cost on the H₂ production cost (IEA, 2019a). In TIMES-BE, local centralized production with electrolyzers reaches an annual utilization factor of 0.20 in 2040 and 0.22 in 2050, which is much lower than the mentioned threshold. Figure 48 (right) depicts the utilization of the electrolyzer in 2040 and 2050, where it is possible to notice that in both cases the electrolyzers are not used at full capacity for more than 1600 hours per year. This behaviour has an impact on the H₂ price, resulting in prices being the estimated import price in most of the hours of the year (see Figure 48). Nevertheless, the time when the electrolyzer is operating coincides with the availability of clean and cheap electricity in the system, this enables the local production of H₂ cheaper than the imported one (see Figure 49). Moreover, there is a trade-off between operating hours and electricity price as can be seen in Figure 50. Certain price conditions make it possible to halve the operating hours of the electrolyzer and produce H₂ at a similar price. For instance, 4000 operating hours and €40/MWh lead to a similar price to 2000 hours and €21/MWh.

Figure 48. H₂ price in the energy system (left) and electrolyzer utilization factor (right).

Hourly hydrogen production in 2050

Figure 49. Hourly hydrogen production in 2050.

Finally, since PtG continues to be a relevant research topic, VITO/SEB will continue exploring in more detail the role of molecules in the energy system in the PROCURA project²⁸. In this project, as part of the transition found projects, a more detailed TIMES-BE model will be developed and used to provide further and more detailed insights regarding the use of molecules to accommodate more VRES and provide flexibility to the energy system, as well as molecules end uses such as H₂ based heat, chemical feedstock and synthetic fuels.

Figure 50. Hydrogen production price as a function of electricity price and operating hours. Based on IEA's estimated techno-economic data for 2030 (IEA, 2019b).

Note: Parameters from IEA Future of hydrogen. CAPEX: €700/kWe, OPEX: 1.5%CAPEX, lifetime: 20 years, return rate: 8%, efficiency: 69% (IEA, 2019b).

²⁸ The PROCURA project looks at the role of power-to-X in multi-energy systems and markets. Scenario studies worldwide show that Power-to-x (gas (e.g. H₂, Methane), chemicals, liquid fuels) and Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) can become crucial technologies in achieving decarbonisation of our energy system by 2050 and increasing security of supply. This project will deliver a roadmap for these novel technologies for all sectors in Belgium, giving a clear view what steps are needed by 2030 to reach carbon neutrality by 2050. <https://procurabelgium.be/en>.

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